

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Special Education: Personalizing Learning for Students with Unique Needs

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the development of computer systems that can perform tasks such as learning, problem-solving, reasoning and perception that typically require human intelligence; it has the potential to significantly impact special education by tailoring learning experiences to individual students' unique needs, abilities and learning styles. Students with unique needs often face challenges in traditional educational settings such as limited accessibility; insufficient support; difficulty with engagement. The absence of AI-powered tools can exacerbate these challenges; making it more difficult for the students to access education and reach their full potential. AI can help bridge the above gaps by providing personalized learning experiences, assistive technology, enhanced accessibility and data-driven insights. By leveraging AI; special educators and students with unique needs can benefit from more effective, efficient and personalized learning experiences. This paper therefore, focused its discourse on "artificial intelligence in special education: personalizing learning for students with unique needs." In doing so, some salient issues such as understanding the concepts of artificial intelligence, special education, and students with unique needs have been highlighted. Also, highlighted include the potentials of artificial intelligence; potential of artificial intelligence in special education and possible ways in which artificial intelligence is tailoring learning for students with unique needs. Artificial intelligence has the potential to transform special education by providing tailor-made learning experiences, improving accessibility and enhancing student outcomes. In conclusion, the paper stated that the roles of artificial intelligence in special education; particularly in personalizing learning for students with unique needs in Nigerian schools cannot be overemphasized. Nevertheless, it noted that despite the advances and potentials of artificial intelligence in personalizing learning for students with unique needs; there are limits to what it can do. Artificial intelligence is incapable of true creativity or innovation; hence, it is based on algorithms and patterns, whereas human creativity is driven by intuition, inspiration and imagination. Nevertheless, the paper recommended the integration of artificial intelligence in special education as it can transform the way special education programmes and services were delivered to students with unique needs; making teaching and learning processes of this category of students more effective and personalized.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, special education, personalized learning, and students with unique needs.

Introduction

The term, "artificial intelligence" was coined in 1956 and in 1959; the first artificial intelligence laboratory was established for research purposes. Thus, machine learning and artificial intelligence had been thought of long time ago. However, a remarkable event occurred in 2011 when IBM's

question answering systems, Watson defeated two greatest jeopardy champions – Brad Ruther and Ken Jennings (Ojha, 2022). Thus, artificial intelligence (AI) appears to have covered the way from hypothetical situation to an important technology. However, the need for machine learning which is a part of artificial intelligence arose due to cloud data, internet, social media and a lot of data gathered and needed to be analyzed. Hence, artificial intelligence (AI) entails the development of computer system that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence such as learning, problem-solving, decision making and perception.

The AI system acquires information and rules for using the information and reasoning, where the system uses rules to reach approximate or definite conclusions and self-correction (Yaghi, 2023). Hence, AI systems can analyze data, identify patterns and make predictions of decision, often with greater speed and accuracy than humans. It has numerous applications in various fields including healthcare, finance, education, transportation and entertainment. Indeed, AI is rapidly revolutionizing various aspects of human lives, and the field of special education is not an exception. Special education depicts an appropriately determined educational sub-system with in-built aspects for prevention and or reduction of apparent learning problems or for accelerating apparent learning assets. It means education designed to facilitate the learning of students who, for a wide variety of reasons; require additional support and adaptive pedagogical methods in order to participate and meet learning objectives in an educational programme. Reasons may include (but are not limited to) disadvantages in physical, behavioural, intellectual, emotional and social capacities. However, educational programmes in special education may follow a similar curriculum as that offered in the comparative regular education system; but may take students' unique needs into consideration by providing specific resources (such as specially trained personnel, equipment or space) and if appropriate, modified educational content or learning objectives. Obani (2006) defined special education as a specialized teaching, learning, psycho-educational services, training and research meant to enable individuals with disabilities or exceptional conditions to maximize their capacities for life endeavours. The foregoing discourse could be accepted as the meaning of special education in the context of this paper.

Students with unique needs portray individuals with disabilities such as those with hearing impairment, learning disabilities, visual impairment, physical impairment, autism spectrum syndrome, or those with intellectual impairment or intellectual precocity (such as the gifted). All these and more learners with unique needs are beneficiaries of special education. The education of students with unique needs has transcended from use of assistive technologies such as text-to-text applications to image recognition and gesture-based interfaces; but an artificial intelligence (AI)-powered assistive technologies seem to offer a wide range of tools to assist students with unique needs in accessing and engaging with instructional contents.

The United Nations Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for persons with disabilities cited in Iroegbu (2023); emphasized active participation and equality of education for all learners. Hence, the mission and vision of special education for students with unique needs may become a mirage without artificial intelligence. For instance, artificial intelligence brings about positive learning outcomes for learners with autism spectrum syndrome as it tends to help them learn more effectively. Yaghi (2023) corroborated that AI-powered tutors can help learners with autism to improve their mathematics and reading skills.

Problem Statement

The problem of this paper is that students with unique needs often face challenges in traditional educational settings such as limited accessibility; insufficient support; difficulty with engagement.

The absence of AI-powered tools seems to exacerbate these challenges; making it more difficult for the students to access education and reach their full potential. AI can help bridge the above gaps by providing personalized learning experiences, assistive technology, enhanced accessibility and data-driven insights. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in special education is personalizing learning for students with unique needs in Nigeria in that by educators can now create more inclusive and supportive learning environments that cater for the diverse needs of the students. Students with unique needs present special challenges that require innovative solutions such as could be envisaged through the application of artificial intelligence. AI comes into play here as it presents potential opportunities to enhance and transform teaching and learning experiences for students with unique needs by making it more accessible, effective and personalized. Some examples of AI that have enhanced and transformed teaching and learning experiences for students with unique needs include virtual assistants like ‘myself’, ‘image recognition systems’ and ‘natural language processing tools.’ However, the focus of this paper is on artificial intelligence in special education and how it is personalizing learning for students with unique needs

The writers therefore, shall focus attention on salient issues such as understanding the concepts of artificial intelligence, special education, students with unique needs, potentials of artificial intelligence (PAI), potentials of artificial intelligence in special education, possible ways in which AI is personalizing learning for students with unique needs, conclusion and suggestions.

Understanding the Concept of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems; which deal with the study and design of an intelligent that perceives its environment and takes actions thereby maximizing its chances of success. In other words, AI is an agent that holds seeming different ideas in mind simultaneously and precisely at the same time. These developments might have originated from the fact that human needs are endless and to meet them, ‘needs-aware’ intelligent systems are necessary. These processes include learning; where the system acquires information and rules for using the information, reasoning; where the system uses rules to reach approximate or definite conclusions and self-corrections (Iroegbu et al, 2024). The father of artificial intelligence, John McCarthy defined it as the science and engineering of making intelligent machines. It is the branch of computer science that deals with study and design of intelligent agents that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chances of success (Singh et al., 2013). More so, it has the ability to hold two different ideas in mind at the same time and still retain the ability to function.

AI includes the learning from past experience, reasoning for decision making, inference power and quick response. It has the ability to take decision on the basis of priorities and tackle complexity and ambiguity; thus, machines programmed by man to carry out tasks; when carried out by humans would require intelligence are said to possess artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is simply the handling of complicated tasks by machines, which were ordinarily handled by humans. It is about doing human intelligent tasks by computing machines but faster and with a reduced error rate (Wang, Lin & Shao, 2023). The scientific goal of artificial intelligence is to understand intelligence by building computer programmes that exhibit intelligent behaviour using symbolic inferences or reasoning inside the machine (Iroegbu et al, 2024). However, the definition of artificial intelligence is not time independent; it gives the judgment of any system by keeping time in mind.

Ordinary programming languages do not have abilities to deal with qualitative information; so all AI machines are programmed to work with their own developed programming language to manipulate knowledge more efficiently (Singh et al, 2013). Subsequently, AI programs are different

from ordinary programming languages thus, they are written to manipulate predominantly qualitative rather than numeric information. Hence, AI is an evolving technology that tries to stimulate human intelligence using machines. It encompasses various subfields including machine learning and deep learning, which allow systems to learn and adapt in novel ways from training.

Concept of Special Education

Special education may be referred to as a customized approach to teaching that supports students with diverse learning needs. It is an integral part of the general education that is designed to help students with unique needs achieve their educational goals by providing tailored instruction, resources and strategies that address their individual needs and challenges. It is modified programme which involves some unique tool, techniques and research efforts in improving instructional arrangement to meet the needs of exceptional children (Narik, 2011); (students with unique need in the context of this paper).

Special education can be provided in either the general schools or in special arrangement or schools; however, the early history of special education is that of separate schools for students with unique needs, especially for those who were blind or deaf. Whatever, the problem, the solution was to put the student in a class with others with similar problems; which amounted to the exclusion of these categories of students from the mainstream of the society. Thus separate became one of the meanings associated with special education; however, as society's response to students with unique needs gradually began to shift away from education ethics of special classes began to express doubts there came special education.

In accelerating the special education programme; extra time might be devoted by the same teacher or by an expert in the concerning field when a project is taken for a student with unique needs, the student may be directed to attend his/her regular classes and participate in all the curricular and co-curricular activities of the school (Barik, 2011). In addition, the student might be assigned with extra consultation hours in the school with the counselor or school guidance officer or with the specific teacher to go through his unique needs. The students with some difficulties may be included in the class without any necessity for those who do not have unique needs to attend to it. However, it is imperative to note that with such kind of designed programme, the students with unique needs achieve a great deal of success in their personal and academic engagements.

Students with unique needs – who are they?

Students with unique needs are learners with disabilities such as those with hearing impairment, learning disabilities, visual impairment, physical impairment, autism spectrum syndrome, or those with intellectual impairment or intellectual precocity (such as the gifted). They are characterized by disabilities (such as physical, cognitive, sensory or mental health that impact learning); learning difficulties (conditions such as dyslexia, dyscalculia or dysgraphia that affect academic performance); developmental delays (delays in cognitive, social or physical development); giftedness (exceptional abilities or talents that require specialized instruction); cultural or linguistic diversity (such as students who may require support due to language barrier or cultural differences); chronic medical conditions (conditions like diabetes, epilepsy or asthma that require management in the educational setting) and mental health needs (students experiencing anxiety, depression or other mental health concerns). These students are beneficiaries of special education in that they all require:

Individualized Instruction: Tailored teaching approaches in order to meet their unique needs

Accommodations: adjustments to instruction, assessments of environment to ensure access to learning.

Support services: Additional services such as speech therapy, occupational therapy or counseling.
Assistive technology Devices (ATD): Tools, equipment or software designed to help students with unique needs perform daily tasks; improve their quality of life and increase their independence. ATD can enhance mobility (such as wheelchairs, walkers, canes and prosthetic limbs); improve communication (such as augmentative and alternative devices); support daily living (such as adaptive utensils, bathing and dressing aids); facilitate learning (such as text-to-speech and speech to text software and specialized keyboards) and promote accessibility (such as screen readers, Braille displays and closed captions).

Potentials Of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

AI can induce, detect and sometimes guess data as well as reconsider decisions by employing back tracking for solutions. AI uses declarative knowledge that is assertions whose true-value is independent of the algorithmic context (Yaghi, 2023). Artificial Intelligence is a technology that enables machines to perform tasks that would normally require human intelligence. It is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer sciences. The term “AI” was coined in 1956, but has become more popular today due to increased data volumes, advanced algorithms and improvements in computing power and storage (Iroegbu et al, 2024). While artificial intelligence has been around in some form for several decades, recent advances in computing power and data analysis have led to its rapid acceleration in development. Today, it is used in various applications, from self-driving cars to practical personal assistants.

According to Andrew, a co-founder of Google Brain and founder of deeplearning.ai:

It is difficult to think of a major industry that artificial intelligence will not transform. This includes healthcare, education, transportation, retail, communications and agriculture. There are surprisingly clear paths for artificial intelligence to make a big difference in these industries.

The foregoing viewpoints tend to emphasize the fact that AI can indeed help humans make more informed decisions by analyzing huge amounts of data; identifying patterns and trends that humans might miss. Artificial intelligence can be especially useful in healthcare and finance, where making accurate predictions and diagnoses can have life-changing implications. It can help humans to automate repetitive and routine tasks; thus, freeing up time and energy for more creative and meaningful works. Thus, it improves efficiency and productivity in many industries from manufacturing to customer service. It also enables humans to create new products and services that were previously impossible by combing data and insights in new and innovative ways. Above all, it has huge exciting possibilities and so far human beings have just had a scratch on the surface of what artificial intelligence technology can do.

Nevertheless, artificial intelligence has huge potential, but it still requires human input to perform appropriately and make decisions to ambiguous situations. Definitely, it is not a replacement for human intelligence, but assistance to humans to responsibly and ethically achieve their goals. Furthermore, human intelligence brings a wide range of experiences, creativity and intuition to the decision-making process that artificial intelligence cannot duplicate. Although, artificial intelligence may process huge amount of data and identify patterns that humans may miss, but it cannot replace the value of human intuition and creativity in decision-making. Therefore, artificial intelligence can never replace human intelligence, but can extend it. Hence, it assists humans in making better decisions and becoming more productive.

In order to ensure that artificial intelligence does not override but enhance the ability to learn through research, students should engage in research activities to be able to make artificial

intelligence systems to thoroughly explain their decisions to humans; align the interests of machines and humans; teach machines about human behaviours and values. Furthermore, students should search for an economic future where humans still have jobs and keep super-smart weapon systems under human control; track condition where a human-artificial intelligence system should be responsive to the human moral reasons relevant in all circumstances; combine the strengths of artificial intelligence and human curiosity to achieve outstanding results in scientific pursuit through research.

It is noteworthy that while artificial intelligence has potential to transform many industries and improve human lives in many ways, it cannot replace human intelligence entirely. It may perform specific tasks more quickly and accurately than humans, but lacks the same level of general intelligence, creativity and social understanding that humans possess. Thus, the most effective and responsive approach to artificial intelligence is to view it as tool to boost human intelligence rather than a replacement for it.

Potentials of Artificial Intelligence (AI) In Special Education

In the special education system, AI can take on several roles which have become more vital with the advent of data analysis involving use of artificial intelligence to analyze the learner's performance; data to detect patterns, predict outcomes and provide actionable insights (Yaghi, 2023). Artificial intelligence has proven beneficial particularly in special education where data-driven decision-making is essential. It can automate administrative tasks, assist students with learning at their own paces, provide personalized learning experiences and offer tutors and teachers valuable insights about students' performance. Thus, artificial intelligence holds tremendous potentials in special education and its clientele.

Artificial intelligence in special education system, can take on several roles such as automatic administrative tasks; assist students with unique learning needs at their own paces, provide personalized learning experiences and offer tutors and teachers valuable insights about the students' performance. More so, AI seems to have potential to significantly enhance the education of students with unique needs by offering personalized instruction, support and data-driven analysis that caters for the unique needs of the students; transforming the learning experiences of students with thoughtful implementation and providing inclusive and effective teaching and learning for them (Yaghi, 2023).

AI-technology holds tremendous promise for enhancing learning and teaching processes of student with unique needs through its ability to create adaptive and personalized learning environment, fostering accessibility and addressing learning styles. Its role in education with reference to special education has grown even more vital with the advent of data analysis, which involves use of artificial intelligence to analyze students' performance, detect patterns, predict outcomes and provide actionable insights (Singh, Vedrtam & Sagar, 2013). So, the application of AI in special education is not just about technology but transforming the way teaching and learning activities are engaged; making education in general and special education in particular more accessible, personalized and effective. It can offer personalized learning experiences, adapt the unique learning needs and capacities of each learner with unique needs. Hence, personalization in this regard, can maximize learning outcomes and facilitate skills development in learners with unique needs.

In the same manner, artificial intelligence can augment assistive technology. For example, AI-powered speech recognition tools can help learners with speech impairment communicate effectively. AI-powered productive text tools can also assist learners with dyslexia in writing. Moreover, AI can enhance accessibility by translating text into speech for learners with visual

impairment and interpret speech into text for those with hearing impairment. It can aid data analysis for instance, AI algorithms can analyze learners' data to identify learning patterns; predict performance and suggest personalized learning paths. It is not an overstatement to say that the potential of artificial intelligence in special education extends beyond its applications. Continuous advancements in artificial intelligence technology no doubts, promise even more innovative solutions to the challenges in special education and for learners with unique needs in inclusive classroom settings in Nigerian schools.

Possible Ways in Which Artificial Intelligence is Personalizing Learning for Students with Unique Needs

By harnessing the potentials of artificial intelligence; helping learners with unique needs in their learning process becomes easy. The development of the AI-technology is not only making education for learners with special needs more accessible but also empower them to participate more fully in the learning activities. This is further discussed below.

Improved Accessibility: Artificial intelligence can greatly improve accessibility in special needs education; making learning materials more easily available to learners with special needs. For instance, AI can be used to convert traditional textbooks into accessible formats such as audio-books or digital texts with adjustable font sizes. More so, AI-powered analytical examinations can help educators to identify potential learning obstacles and provide timely intervention. By analyzing data on learners' performance and behaviour, artificial intelligence can predict which learners might be at risk of falling behind and suggest strategies to help them catch up. In addition, AI-powered assistive technology helps students with unique needs such as the visual or hearing impairment; access learning materials and participate in the classroom teaching and learning processes. This proactive approach can lead to better learning outcomes and possibly foster a more inclusive educational environment for students with unique needs.

Personalized Learning: AI has the potential to transform the learning experiences of students with unique needs by providing personalized learning paths that are tailor-made to each student's needs. Through the advanced algorithms and machine learning, AI can analyze students' learning patterns, strengthens weakness and adapt their educational content accordingly. This approach can however, be particularly beneficial to students with unique needs who often require a more robust individualized approach to learning. AI-powered tools like Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) can provide personalized instruction and feedback; thus, helping the students to progress at their own paces. They can also identify areas where students might be struggling and adapt the learning materials to suit their unique learning needs. Therefore, personalized learning can result to a more engaging and effective learning experiences helping special education and its clientele to reach their full potential.

Assistive Technology (AT): AI plays a crucial role in the development of assistive technology for special education clientele. For example, from speech recognition software to AI-powered prosthetics, these technologies can greatly enhance the learning and living experience of students with unique needs. In another development, AI-powered assistive technology can tailor learning experiences to individual student's needs, abilities and learning styles.

Creating Adaptive Learning Environments: The integration of artificial intelligence technologies hold promise for creating adaptive learning environments, fostering accessibility and addressing each learner's learning styles. The potential of AI is being recognized by educators and researchers worldwide. The technology promises to bring about significant changes to the way special needs education service deliverables are handled; making it more personalized, effective and accessible.

Upholding Human Rights and Promoting Inclusive Education: The European Nations are progressively dedicated to upholding human rights and promoting inclusive education. However, the enduring disparities in education and social opportunities suggest an inconsistent application of inclusive education (Toyokawa et al., 2023). The application of AI has had a dual effect not only on learners with unique needs but also on educational institutions by facilitating the development of inclusive teaching methods (Melo-Lopez et al., 2025)

Real-time Support: AI-powered assistive technology can provide real-time support and accommodations; enabling students with unique needs to learn more effectively.

Increased Independence: AI-powered assistive technologies such as text-to-speech or speech-to-text software can empower students with unique needs to work independently, building confidence and self-reliance.

Enhanced Engagement: AI-powered assistive technology can make learning more engaging and interactive; thus, increasing the motivation and participation students'. AI possesses the capacity to profoundly transform how teachers engage with learners with special needs. The influence of AI and other technologies has extended far across various industries including academia. The advancement has significantly facilitated the learning process for learners with unique needs such as those with sensory, motor, cognitive and other disabilities.

Conclusion

The paper aimed at highlighting and discussing artificial intelligence in special education: personalizing learning for students with unique needs. The roles of artificial intelligence in special education; particularly in personalizing learning for students with unique needs in Nigerian schools cannot be overemphasized. By providing personalized learning experiences, improving accessibility and developing assistive technologies, artificial intelligence is poised to revolutionizing special education frontiers. As continuous effort is geared towards exploring the potential of artificial intelligence in the field of special education and in personalizing learning for its clientele; it is important for special educators, parents and students with unique needs to stay informed and embrace the opportunities that artificial intelligence technology brings.

Nevertheless, it is important to note that despite the advances and potentials of artificial intelligence in personalizing learning for students with unique needs; there are limits to what it can do. A major limitation is that it is only as good as the data it is trained on such that if data are biased or incomplete the system will reflect those biases and limitations. The implication is that it is incapable of true creativity or innovation; it can generate new ideas and solutions based on existing data, but cannot think outside the box and create original ideas. Hence, it is based on algorithms and patterns, whereas human creativity is driven by intuition, inspiration and imagination.

Recommendations

As the integration of artificial intelligence in special education continue to evolve, it is crucial to look ahead to what the future may hold. For instance, looking forward to the emerging trends and understanding potential challenges in educational inclusion of students with unique needs in Nigeria; it is possible that every student regardless of his/her individual unique needs; has the opportunity to learn, grow and even thrive in inclusive education system. Thus, the integration of artificial intelligence in special education can transform the way special education programmes and services are delivered; thus, making teaching and learning processes more personalized, effective and inclusive for students with unique needs. Invariably, the application of AI in education of students with unique needs may have inevitable benefits, which are summarized below.

1. Assist in the diagnosis of learning and language disabilities using machine learning algorithms as expert systems.
2. AI-powered robotic assistance can help learners with autism spectrum syndrome disorder (ASD) to develop social skills and understand emotions for instance; AI-powered tutors can help learners with autism to improve their reading and mathematics skills.
3. AI-powered tools such as Microsoft translator, which can translate speech into captions for learners to see; can help learners with hearing impairment.
4. Artificial intelligence such as virtual and augmented reality tools can help learners with visual impairment to improve their learning experiences.
5. AI-powered tools can help learners with physical impairment to access educational services and maintain their autonomy during educational courses.

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